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Therapeutic effect of pomegranate peel extract on heme oxygen-free 1 (HO-1) and angiotensin-converting enzyme-2 (ACE-2) in the kidney tissue of mice treated with mitomycin [Rats, 2023; 1(2): 27-34]

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Erratum

Unfortunately, the original version of this article¹ incorrectly placed the 50 µm magnified figures in Figures 2a and 2d on the plate. The figures are replaced with each other. The captions for Figures 2 and 3 in this figure also contained errors. These have been corrected. These edits have been corrected in the original article and are also correctly included below.

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Figure 2. HO-1 immunoreactivity in mouse kidney tissue. a) Control Group, b) MMC Group, c) MMC+150PP Group, d) MMC+300PP Group. Arrow: Glomerulus, Arrow head: Distal Tubule, Small arrow: Proximal Tubule. IHC Staining.

Figure 3. ACE-2 immunoreactivity in mouse kidney tissue. a) Control Group, b) MMC Group, c) MMC+150PP Group, d) MMC+300PP Group. Arrow: Glomerulus, Arrow head: Distal Tubule, Small arrow: Proximal Tubule. IHC Staining.

Reference

1. Gündoğdu H, Uluman E, Eliş Yıldız S, Aksu Kılıçlı P, Gezer A, Karadağ Sarı E. Therapeutic effect of pomegranate peel extract on heme oxygen-free 1 (HO-1) and angiotensin-converting enzyme-2 (ACE-2) in the kidney tissue of mice treated with mitomycin. *Rats.* 2023; 1(2): 27-34 Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10444360